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Housing Deficit, the Decadent of Nigerian Cities: The Case of Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

Of all problems facing cities in most developing countries of the world today, housing deficit takes centre stage occasioned by rapid population growth and urban expansion.. This study examined housing deficits as a decadent of Nigerian cities, the case of Obio/Akpor Local Government Area of Rivers State. The study adopted the Mixed Method Research Approach and employed the triangulation research design. Purposive sampling technique was used to select sampled respondents and the communities under investigation. One hundred (100) respondents was arrived at with the aid of Taro Yamane formula. Qualitative and quantitative data were collected concurrently and analysed using univariate summary statistic and content analysis revalidation technique. The study revealed the causes of housing deficit to include; rapid population growth and urbanisation, high cost of building materials, lack of access to affordable housing finance; the effects of housing deficits to include; the emergent of squatter settlements. the development of slum housing and overcrowding of residential environment. The study therefore recommended that the State and National Assembly should carry out the review and implementation of the national housing policy to ensure equitable and sustainable provision of housing units to close the gap between housing supply and demand in the area.

Keywords: Housing, Deficit, Decadent, Nigerian cities

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Housing, literally defines buildings or other shelters in which people live, a place to live, and a dwelling of inhabitation. To nations, it is a critical component in social and economic system (Obashoro-John, 2002). Housing represents one of the most basic human needs. To most groups, housing means shelter but to others, it means more as it serves as one of the best indicators of a person's standard of living and his or her place in the society (Nubi, 2008). It is a priority for the attainment of living standard and it is important to both rural and urban dwellers. These attributes make demand for housing to know no bound as population growth and urbanization are increasing very rapidly and the gap between housing need and supply becomes widen.

Housing deficit has become a problem and continued to accumulate over the years as a result of poor housing policy implementation by successive Governments in Nigeria and neglect by government to provide affordable housing units for its citizens. Cultural factors such as preferences and values or social

status, taste and financial resources, also influences the physical characteristics of housing and its provision. There has been phenomenal increase in human population especially of city dwellers without a corresponding increase in housing provision which have consequently led to acute shortage of habitable dwelling units in Nigeria. The resultant effects are deplorable environment, overcrowding, inadequate and poor infrastructure, homelessness, poor living conditions, increased rate of poverty and its concomitant social vices (Ademiluyi & Rayi, 2008)

Obviously, the provision of adequate housing for everyone as opined by Ubale, Martin & Wee (2013) requires actions not only by Governments, but by all sectors of the society including the private sectors, non-Governmental organizations, communities and local authorities, as well as partner organizations and entities of the international community.

In developing countries such as Nigeria, poor housing delivery has been attributed to inadequate mechanisms and systems for land allocation, funding, mortgage financing and infrastructure (Encarta, 2007). Thus, as Nigeria is perhaps, one of the fastest urbanizing country in the African continent, one of the most pressing problem she is facing is lack of affordable housing accommodation. As more and more Nigerians make towns and cities their homes, the resulting social, economic, environmental and political challenges need to be greatly addressed (Raji, 2008). A study of housing situation in Nigeria put existing housing stock at 23 housing units per 1000 inhabitant (Ibem & Amole, 2010). Housing deficit is put at 15 million houses (Mabogunje, 2007), while ₦12 trillion will be required to finance the deficit. This is about four (4) times the Annual National Budget of Nigeria (Federal Housing Authority (FHA, 2010). Under the National Housing Fund (NHF) programme initiated in 1994, to produce 121,000 housing units, it was believed that less than 5% was achieved. In spite of series of Government policies towards housing delivery, there exist a gap between housing supply and demand.

In Rivers State generally and in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area in particular, one of the local Government areas that make up Port Harcourt metropolis, the fastest urbanizing centre in the Niger Delta area of Nigeria, the problem of affordable housing has been a concern for both the Government and individuals. Appreciating this problem of housing deficit in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area, the Federal government has made efforts through the National Housing Policy (NHP) to bridge the gap between housing supply and demand, and solve the problem of housing deficit in the area

2.0 RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Concept of Housing Deficit

The concept and origin of housing deficit, which refers to the excess of housing demand over the supply, can be closely associated with urbanization. Housing demand rarely surpasses its supply in a traditional rural setting where the housing standards can be met with materials that are affordable by nearly all (Sanusi, 2018). In a traditional rural setting, members of the society that needs to build houses can afford it with help from peers and family members. In urban areas, however, families ability to acquire housing depends on, among other factors, income level, availability and the cost of housing. In addition, the growth and demand for housing in the urban centres, unlike in the rural areas, depends not only on the natural population growth, but also on rural-urban migrations, economic activities that attract labour force from other cities, among others. Giving the rising pace for housing demand, the supply of housing stock, however, depends on and is constrained by a number of factors, including financing, availability of land, cost of building materials, regulatory permits, as well as infrastructure provisions (Sengupta & Sharma, 2008). These determinants of housing supply, for a given demand, constrain the development of building stock relative to the demand, thereby creating housing deficit.

Housing deficit can be conceptualized mostly on urban phenomenon, and can also be conceptualized as resulting from two types of demands, hence, segmenting the market into two (Sanusi, 2018). These are the market for rented accommodation, which serves the need of distinct clients (for example, starter families and city workers with short term residency) and the market for owner occupied housing. This distinction is important because addressing deficits in the two segments requires distinct strategies on the demand and supply sides. For instance, eliminating the deficit in rented accommodation could require incentivizing investors to raise the stock of rented accommodation with a good mix of low-cost and

high-end housing. Closing the deficit for home ownership requires supporting families to access affordable finance, as well as, supporting developers to build affordable housing. In principle therefore, eliminating the housing deficit in Nigeria requires both supply-side (investors and property developers) and demand-side (off-takes/families) measures.

2.2 Causes of Housing Deficit

The importance of housing in the economic and social development of a nation cannot be overemphasized. Housing is a key element in the generation of economic growth and development. As a result, it has had strong positive impact on the growth and development of many societies in the world but this is not yet the case in Ghana and other African countries (Afrane, Bujang, Limau & Kasin, 2016). The scenario is even worse in Nigeria considering the available data on the shortfall in housing supply which is less commensurable with the demand, thus creating housing deficit (Yeboah, 2015). The housing deficit situation in Ghana fall short of the provision standard of affordable housing for the mass of the population and this has remained a major challenge for many countries. Several intervention measures have been seen as the way to remedy the ever growing demands which far outstrip the supply creating an acute shortage. Unfortunately, the shortage of housing continue to be one of the most crucial socio-economic challenges facing these countries, Nigeria been one of the worst hit (National Housing Policy (NHP, 2012).

The causes of housing deficit according to Afrane, et al., (2016) are linked to several conditions. The lack of continuity due to consistent change of Government has made many African countries to suffer a setback in the provision of public housing. The result has contributed to the housing situation facing the countries at the moment. For instance, in seeking to boost housing supply, the Government of Ghana in the year 2005 pursued various programmes such as the affordable housing programme to build over 100,000 housing units through private public partnership (PPP) across the country Bank of Ghana, 2007. However, just after a change of Government in the year 2009, all the projects have been abandoned and left to squatters up till now with no tangible reason given to complete them. This housing project when completed in any case could have accommodated hundreds of families.

Another cause of housing deficit in African countries is the increased rate of rural-urban migrations. There is an unprecedented movement of people from the rural areas to the urban centers and this according to UN-Habitat (2014) has increased the pressure on urban housing. Consequently, the provision of housing has scarcely moved in tandem with demand, leading to pockets of slums and communities that seem to consist entirely of kiosks, containers and little shanties by way of plumbing or drainage. Specifically (UN-Habitat, 2014) noted that, this can illustrate a situation of urban poverty especially in major cities and towns. For instance, in the year 2005, as a result of acute shortage of housing and poor conditions of housing, sub-Saharan African had 199 million slum dwellers constituting 20% of the world's total slum population and had the highest urban growth rate of 4.5% and the high annual slum growth rate of 4.53%. However, Ghana in the same year has 5.4 million slum dwellers and is anticipated to reach 7.1 million by 2020 and Nigeria also 5.61 million slum dwellers with a 3.2% annual growth rate and is estimated to hit over 50 million with growth rate of 5.8% Ametete, Aboagye & Sarpong – Kumankom, (2011) have also identified population growth and urbanization, inadequate mortgage financing institution, high cost of land and building materials, defective land tenure system, high cost of land acquisition and lack of infrastructures and provision of utility services as other causes of housing deficit in the urban and rural areas of the African sub-continent. This position was also collaborated by Appiah (2012) who noted that multiplicities of factors such as poor Governance, high level of unemployment and poverty among the citizens, high cost of building materials and land acquisition; bureaucratic bottlenecks in landed property acquisition, corruption on the part of those in Government, high population and lack of will power on the part of Government towards the provision of housing units for all are causative factors for housing deficit.

2.3 Problems Associated with Housing Deficit

The issue of housing deficit has denied urban dwellers the benefits of affordable and sustainable housing. According to Encart (2017), housing deficit has resulted to unsanitary, unhygienic, unsafe and inadequate housing which can affect the security, physical health and privacy of man. Okafor (2016)

asserts that housing all over the world has remained an interdependent phenomenon that faces mankind and it represent one of the most basic human needs which no doubts, has a profound impact on the health, welfare and productivity of every individual irrespective of social and economic status, colour or creed. Thus, housing deficit is one of the social problems bred by capitalism manifested as a particular form of housing need with the growth of the urban population and the transformation of a dwelling into a commodity; there is a sharp deterioration in the working of people's living conditions and huge rise in apartment (Faith, 2014).

Housing problem are manifested in the emergent of squatter settlements and the development of slums, overcrowding residential environments, poor and inadequate social amenities, unsatisfactory and unwholesome environmental conditions and urban squator, the absence of space, the poor development of land area leading to overcrowding of building inaccessibility within residential areas and in scarcity and high cost of building materials (Enisen & Ogundiran, 2013). The study conducted by Human Development Nigeria (HDN, 2006), reveals that the problem of housing deficit results mainly from unprecedented growth of urban population. In Nigeria, according to this source, states with the largest population of urban dwellers far in excess of the national average are Lagos (94%), Oyo (69%), Anambra (62%) and Rivers (60%). The inevitable outcome of this explosion is the aggregation of urban blight and squatters, resulting in the majority of urban dwellers living under sub-human conditions in squatter settlements, especially those without employment and any viable means of livelihood (Igwe, Okeke, Onwuruah, Nwafor & Umeh, 2017).

Severe shortages of housing made people stay at water fronts which serve as hide out for their notorious and criminal minded activities. Thus, Igwe et al, (2017) have observed that the increased emergent of urban crime and criminality stemmed from the acute housing deficit that are prevalent in most city centers in the world. In either case, and in some instances, the nature of the problems of housing shortage have from that of deficit to that of affordability, accessibility and inability of certain groups in the population to obtain decent housing accommodation..

2.3.5 Environmental Effects of Housing Deficit

The level and extent of housing deficit to a large extent affects the housing environment and condition in the region or a particular area. Studies by Okafor (2016; Jane, Boardeme, Botrill, Darby, Mark, Killip, Larberry & Loved, 2006) have shown that the extent and level of housing shortages is an indication of environmental degradation and deterioration going by the abysmal and terrible housing conditions that are found in some places. When there are shortages (deficit in housing provision), there is bound for the emergent of squatter settlements to spring up as well as the development slums. The characteristics features and indicators of deficit in housing provision are that of over crowedness of housing units, lack of setback standards, no drainage, lack of social amenities, poor environmental conditions, decay infrastructures, absent of electricity and water supply services, high level of waste generation, improper waste disposal, surface and ground water contamination, outbreak of diseases, hide out for criminal element, and the exploded population index (HDN, 2006).

One serious problem of uncontrolled urbanization and environmental quality had been revealed by the index of housing. Shortage of housing accommodation has become an enduring feature of the urbanization process especially in countries of developing world. Occupancy ratio is a parameter that is usually accepble for measuring the level of overcrowding in any given housing situation. For example; there is evidence that the ratio is very high for many countries of the developing world. Occupancy ratio in Lagos is 1:4, in Accra Ghana is 1:3, in Nairobi is about 1:3. The implication of this in terms of housing environment is a demonstration of over crowdedness in terms of persons and gradual slum development.. This is because the building themselves are not well spaced with standard setbacks from one another from the access road. In many cases in Lagos, unapproved space, which are setbacks are constructed upon as housing accommodation. This, phenomenon originates the process of slum in many of these centres

3.0 METHODOLOGY

Study Area

Obio/Akpor Local Government Area (LGA) is one of the area councils that make up the Port Harcourt Metropolis, and one of the twenty three LGAs in Rivers State. It is an economic hotspot in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. The Local Government area covers 260km² and a population of 464,789 Persons (National Population Commission, NPC 2006), and a projected population of 1,443, 937 persons in 2024. It came into being on the 5th day of May, 1989 and has its headquarters at Rumuodamaya. The 1975 Port Harcourt City Master plan which covered both Port Harcourt City Area Council and Obio/Akpor Area Council shows that Obio/Akpor Area Council has a total of 260km² landmass out of which about 45 (17.3km²) of it is wetland area (Oyegun, 2003).

Obio/Akpor Area Council is bounded by Port Harcourt City Local Government Area in the South, Oyigbo in the East, Ikwerre in the North, and Emohua Local Government Areas in the West (See Fig. 1). It is located within latitudes 4^o5'11" and 5^o15'45" North and longitudes 6^o22'25" and 8^o05'12" East (Oyegun, 2003).

Fig. 1: Study Area showing communities

Source: GIS Lab., URP Department, Rivers State University.

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The study adopted the Mixed Method Research Approach and employed the triangulation research design. While Mixed Method Research (MMR) is a research approach that enables the researcher to collect both qualitative and quantitative data from sampled respondents, the triangulation research design combines both data to validate findings and increase confidence in results. In this study, the mixed method research was employed because both quantitative and qualitative data was collected concurrently and results triangulated. Five communities and its residents were purposively selected and studied. The five communities include; Rumueme Federal Housing Estate, Rumubekwe Federal Housing Estate, Bori

Camp, Air Force Base Rumuomasi, and Naval Base Ekemini. The population of the selected communities was projected using the exponential projection model given as $P_n = P_o (1+r)^n$ from 1991 to 2024 to be **14,0213** persons, with an annual growth rate of 6.5%. (NPC, 2006: 2018).

To determine the sample size, the total number of household from the five communities chosen for study was ascertained to be **23369** with an average household size of 6 persons per household. To further determine the number of household heads to be sampled, the Taro Yamane's formula given as;

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

(Yamane, 1967), was applied with a 10% level of precision, and this give 100. The **100**

so ascertain was the total number of households sampled which represent the sample size for the study. The systematic sampling technique was used to distribute the questionnaires across the sampled communities.

Table 1: Population and Sample Size

S/N	Sample Communities			1991 Pop.	2024 Projected	Household Size (6)	% of Pop.	No. of Questionnaire
1.	Federal Housing Estate,	Rumueme		3021	24137	4023	17.2	17
2.	Federal Housing Estate,	Rumubekwe		2006	16028	2671	11.4	11
3.	Bori Camp			10, 168	81240	13540	57.9	58
4.	Air Force Base, Rumuomasi			1,906	15229	2538	10.9	11
5.	Naval Base Ekenmini			448	3579	597	2.6	3
	Total			17549	140213	23369	100	100

Source: Researchers' Survey, 2024

Two (2) key informants each from Federal Ministry of Lands and Housing, Federal Ministry of Urban Development and Physical Planning; and Property developers was purposively selected for sample making a total of six (6) key informants that was interviewed for the study.

Table 2: Key Informants Population

S/N	Key informants	No. of Officials
1.	Federal Ministry of lands and Housing	2
2.	Federal Ministry of urban development and physical planning	2
3.	Property developers	2
	Total	6

Source: Researchers' Survey, 2024

Data were obtained from both primary and secondary sources. Questionnaires were used to collect data from residents of the sampled communities, while checklists was used to obtained useful information from key informants. Univariate summary statistic was used to abstract and analysed data collected from the sampled respondents via questionnaire administration, while content analysis and revalidation techniques was applied to analyse data collected from key informants.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Causes of Housing Deficit

Data on the causes of housing deficit in the study area were collected and analysed and the results presented in table 3. The analysis revealed that different factors accounted for the marked gap between housing supply and demand, a deficit situation in the study area. From the analysis, it is shown that 20.6% of the sampled respondents said housing deficit is cause by lack of access to affordable housing finance, 17.5% said high cost of building materials, 14.4% said inefficient land acquisition processes, 13.4% said rapid population growth and urbanisation, 12.4% said poverty and limited economic opportunities, 11.3% said urban expansion and rural-urban migration, 10.3% suggested unwillingness on

the part of government to provide affordable housing accommodation to her citizens. The implication of the data as presented in table 4.1 suggests to the fact that there a number of factors responsible for housing shortages in the study area. Although lack of access to affordable housing finance and high cost of building materials seems to have high percentage of responses, the baseline issue is traceable to government sensitivity towards affordable housing provision. The federal government, state and private sector housing provisions is grossly inadequate leading to housing shortages in the study area.

Table 3: Distribution of responses on the causes of housing deficit

S/N	Options	F	%
1.	Rapid population growth and urbanisation	13	13.4
2.	High cost of building materials	17	17.5
3.	Lack of access to affordable housing finance	20	20.6
4.	Inefficient land acquisition processes	14	14.4
5.	Poverty and limited economic opportunities	12	12.4
6.	Urban expansion and rural-urban migration	11	11.3
7.	Unwillingness on the part of government to provide affordable housing accommodation to her citizens	10	10.3
	Total	97	100

Source: Researchers’ survey, 2024

Residents’ Rating of Housing Deficit in the Study Area.

The study ascertained the perceptions of respondents concerning the rate of housing deficit in the study area. The analysis shows the various rating options by the respondents. Thus, 22.7% of the respondents rated the level of housing deficit in the area to be very high, 24.7% said it is high, 16.5% said it is moderate, while 18.6% and 11.3% said it is low and very low respectively as shown in table 4.

Table 4: Distribution of Residents’ Rating of the Level of Housing Deficit

S/N	Options	F	%
1.	Very High	22	22.7
2.	High	24	24.7
3.	Moderate	16	16.5
4.	Low	18	18.6
5.	Very Low	11	11.3
	Total	97	100

4.0 Source: Researchers’ survey, 2024

4.3 Problems and Level of Housing Deficit

The study also investigated the problems and the level of housing deficit in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area. Thus, the survey data shows that the problems of housing deficit in the area are many and include unsanitary, unhygienic and unhealthy housing environment as 20.6% of the respondents have attested. Also, 18.6% said the emergent of squatter settlements with unpleasant housing condition is another problem. 16.5% noted that the development of slum housing environment is another problem. 15.5% of them said it leads to overcrowding of residential environment while 14.7% of the sampled respondents noted that housing deficit lead to the emergent of an urban residential decay and pollution while 14.7% said others problems are poor and inadequate social amenities, inaccessibility within the residential areas etc. As shown in Table 5.

5 Table 5: Distribution of Responses on the Problems of Housing Deficit

S/N	Options	F	%
1.	Unsanitary, unhygienic and unhealthy housing environment	20	20.6
2.	The emergent of squatter settlement	18	18.6
3.	The development of slum housing	16	16.5
4.	Overcrowding of residential environment	15	15.5
5.	Urban residential decay and pollution	14	14.7
6.	Others (poor and inadequate social amenities, inaccessibility within the residential areas	14	14.7
	Total	97	100

Source: Researchers' survey, 2024

The study also went further to examine the respondents' responses on other problems of housing deficit in the study area. Hence, the survey data shows that the problems of housing deficit lower the productivity index of the people (18.6%), brings about profound impact on the health and psychosis of the affected people (16.4%), leads to severe effect on the physical status and privacy of a man (15.5%), leads to a condition of poor and inadequate social amenities (14.7%), brings about unsatisfactory and unwholesome urban life experience (13.4%), causes metal derailment (12.4%) and disease outbreak and epidemic (9.3%) as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Distribution of Responses on Problems of Housing Deficit

S/N	Options	F	%
1.	Lowers the productivity index of the people	18	18.6
2.	Leads to profound impact on the health of the resident	16	16.4
3.	Leads to severe effect on the physical status and privacy of a man	15	15.5
4.	Leads to a condition of poor and inadequate social amenities	14	14.7
5.	Unsatisfactory and unwholesome urban life experience	13	13.4
6.	Causes metal derailment	12	12.4
7.	Disease outbreak and epidemic	9	9.3
	Total	97	100

Source: Researchers' Survey, 2024

The study further investigated the current level of housing deficit in the study area. Thus, the study survey data revealed that the existing housing stock stood at 23 per 1000 inhabitant. The area's present housing deficit as at November 2004 was estimated at a staggering 200 units which is about 15.0 percent increase from the figure in November 2020 (Key informant engage, 2024). About ₦65 billion will be required to finance the deficit. With a population of Obio/Akpor as at December 2024 projected to be about 2,101,453 persons using the exponential population projection model, the current deficit is alarmingly high. Thus, housing price and rental values are on the increase ahead of general inflation (key informant engagement, 2024)

4.3.5 Planning Measures to Solving the Problems of Housing Deficit

Sustainable planning measures to solve the problem of housing deficit in the study area was ascertained and the results presented in table 7. The results revealed some of the urban planning measures that can be used to solve the problem of housing overcrowdness and deteriorating housing condition due to housing deficit as; Promote public-private partnership (9.3%), group resettlement (18.6%), aided self-help housing (14.7%), resettlement scheme (15.5%), the establishment of new town strategy (16.4%), Develop affordable housing programmes (12.4%) and others including granting of building permission to investors and housing developers, and making it easier to obtain Certificate of Occupancy (C of O) (13.4%). This planning approach is targeted at improving housing condition and making affordable housing units available for the masses.

Table 7: Distribution of Responses on Urban Planning Strategies to Solving housing Deficit

S/N	Options	F	%
1.	Promote public-private partnership	9	9.3
2.	Resettlement scheme	15	15.5
3.	Enhance access to mortgage financing	18	18.6
4.	Aided self-help housing	14	14.7
5.	New town strategy	16	16.4
6.	Develop affordable housing programmes	12	12.4
7.	Granting of building permission to housing investors and intending housing builders	13	13.4
	Total	97	100

Source: Researchers' Survey, 2024

CONCLUSION

The demand for housing accommodation in cities of the developing world becomes pertinent as the rate of urbanisation keep increasing with more human population leaving in urban areas. Housing shortage becomes a problem in cities where the rate of housing demand is far above the available housing units, causing lots of challenges to the physical and health environment. This study examined the problem of housing deficit in cities of the developing world taking Obio/Akpor area of Rivers state as a case study. The increasing pace of Housing demand in the study area becomes worrisome as pockets of shanties and squatter settlements are found at strategic locations in the city. The study adopted the mix method research approach where qualitative and quantitative data were collected concurrently and analysed. The findings of the study revealed the causes of housing deficits in the study area to be myriad ranging from increasing rate of urbanisation and urban expansion to high cost of building materials and lack of access to affordable housing finance. The findings further showed the problems arising from housing deficit to include; the emergent of squatter settlement, development of slum housing, overcrowding of residential environment, urban residential decay and pollution. However planning measures to curb the problem of housing deficit in the study area have been succinctly ex-rayed with more emphasis on government commitment to the provision of affordable housing units to the general public to march the demand for housing accommodation. Housing provision becomes a major task for both government and the private sectors to make affordable housing available for all.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made;

- i. The State and National Assembly should carry out the review and implement of the national housing policy to ensure equitable and sustainable provision of housing units to close the gap between housing supply and demand in the area.
- ii. The creation of job opportunities to enhance citizens' income, urban-urban migration linkage, reduced urban population strategies should be aggressively pursued and adopted so as to reduce the massive demand in urban housing.
- iii. Massive housing provision, mortgage financing, creating ease of getting access to building permit and land as well as provision for housing loans and subsidies should be done to encourage housing investors and to enhance supply housing provision to cushion the effects of the problems and level of housing deficit in the area.
- iv. Up-to-date urban plans and the effective enforcement of existing master plans to meet current local realties on housing demand.

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